

Safety and Stress Management– A Case Study of Toyota Motor Corporation

Shridevi

Research scholar at Srinivas University

HOD, Department of Commerce

Govinda Dasa College

Surathkal 575014

Karnataka

9535628832

shridevi431@gmail.com

&

Dr. C.K.Hebbar

Research Guide at Srinivas University

Mangalore -575001

919481778349

ABSTRACT

Stress is considered to be an integral part of one's life, especially as the pace of development of increases. Work is a common term which is applied for all sorts of occupation. It is a basic condition for most of people and is an important component of the atmosphere for human survival. The impact of stress on human health is widely recognized. It is a universal principle that people have the right to the highest attainable standards of health. Without health at work a person cannot contribute to society and achieve well being. If health at work is threatened, there is no basis for productive employment and socio-economic development. Psychosocial hazards such as increased competition, higher expectation as regards performance; longer working hours are all contributing to an ever more stressful **working environment**. Stress can also contribute to an increase in workplace accidents. **Work place safety** is very important for each and every employee in the industry because all the workers desire to work in a safe and protected atmosphere. Health and safety is the key factor for all the industries in order to promote the wellness of both employees and employers. Even stress produces numerous physical and mental symptoms which vary

according to each individual's situational factors. These can include physical health decline as well as depression. In today's era of globalization where there is a lot of competition, innovation and change, executives in all organizations cannot avoid tension, stress and anxiety on their day-to-day work. Stress as a negative influence, can result in feelings of disruption, rejection and anger which in turn lead to **health** problems. Stress is sometimes avoidable but sometimes is unavoidable and one has to be aware of certain measures to avoid stress. The process of **stress management** is named as one of the keys to a happy and successful life in modern society. Although life provides numerous demands that can prove difficult to handle, stress management provides a number of ways to manage anxiety and maintain overall well being.

Toyota Motor Corporation is a Japanese multinational automotive manufacturer headquartered in Toyota, Aichi, Japan. Toyota corporate structure consisted of employees worldwide and presently it occupies tenth largest place in the world by its revenue. The aim of the present case study is to find safety and stress management programmes implemented by Toyota Motor Corporation to enhance the wellbeing of their employees.

Key words: Mental health, working environment, work place safety, Stress management.

Introduction

Stress is a part of day-to-day life. It is a common human phenomenon and part of life as an employee in an organisation. Stress is not always negative. It results in two ways called positive and negative stress. The positive dimension of the stress is called a Eustress. It may induce an individual to discover innovative and smarter way of doing things. But usually, the term stress has a negative implication and this negative aspect of stress is called Distress.

Work is a common term which is applied for all sorts of occupation. It is a basic condition for most of people and is an important component of the atmosphere for human survival. The impact of stress on human health is widely recognized. It is a universal principle that people have the right to the highest attainable standards of health. Without health at work a person cannot contribute to society and achieve well being. If health at work is threatened, there is no basis for productive employment and socio-economic development. Psychosocial hazards such as increased competition, higher expectation as regards performance, longer working hours are all contributing to an ever more stressful working environment. Stress can also contribute to an increase in work place accidents. Work place safety is very important for

each and every employee in the industry because all the workers desire to work in a safe and protected atmosphere. Health and safety is the key factor for all the industries in order to promote the wellness of both employees and employers. It is a duty and moral responsibility of the company to look after the employee's protection. These days, work place health and safety procedures are important for the wellbeing of both employees and employers because human loss is immeasurable and intolerable. Even stress produces numerous physical and mental symptoms which vary according to each individual's situational factors. These can include physical health decline as well as depression. In today's era of globalization where there is a lot of competition, innovation and change, executives in all organizations cannot avoid tension, stress and anxiety on their day-to-day work. Stress as a negative influence, can result in feelings of disruption, rejection and anger which in turn lead to health problems. Stress is sometimes avoidable but sometimes is unavoidable and one has to be aware of certain measures to avoid stress. The process of stress management is named as one of the keys to a happy and successful life in modern society. Although life provides numerous demands that can prove difficult to handle, stress management provides a number of ways to manage anxiety and maintain overall well being.

Conceptual frame work

Definition of stress

Dr. Hans Selye defined stress as "the rate of all wear and tear caused by life".

According to Kyriacou (1978), stress is result of prolonged pressures that can't be controlled by the coping strategies that an individual has.

Ellis & Thompson defines stress as "Stress, in addition to being itself, and the result of itself, is also the cause of itself".

Spielberger (1979) defined stress in two different ways. According to him, it is a dangerous potentiality, harmful/unpleasant external situation/conditions (stressors) that produce stress reaction; and secondly the internal thought judgment, emotional state and physiological process that are evoked by stressful stimuli.

Sisk (1977) defined stress as a state of strain, tension or pressure and it is a normal reaction resulting from interaction between the individual and the environment. Strain means to make great demand on something; tension is a mental or emotional strain that makes natural relaxed behaviour impossible; and pressure is a powerful demand on somebody's time, attention or energy.

Types of stress

1. **Acute stress:** Acute stress is most often caused by reactive thinking. Negative thoughts predominate about situations or events that have recently occurred or upcoming situations, events, or demands in the near future.
2. **Episodic acute stress:** The individuals who frequently suffer acute stress often live a life of chaos and crisis. There are always in a rush or feel pressured. They take on many responsibilities, and usually, cannot stay organized with so many time demands.
3. **Chronic stress:** It is the most harmful type of stress. If chronic stress is left untreated over a long period of time, it can significantly and often irreversibly damage your physical health and deteriorate your mental health.

Stress at work place

Stress is a fact of life and can affect individuals in a variety of ways. At some point in life, every individual experiences some degree of stress; some individuals experience stress more often than others and some have difficulty dealing with stress. Stress at work place categorized into four-

Occupation stress: Occupation stress can be physical environment- like noise, light, polluted air, temperature etc.

Individual stressors: It includes role conflict, role ambiguity, work over load, responsibility etc.

Group stressors: Group stressors like- poor relationship with peers, Subordinates etc.

Organizational stressors: It includes poor structural design, no specific policy etc.

Symptoms of stress:

Absenteeism, escaping from work responsibilities, arriving late, leaving early etc; deterioration in work performance, memory loss, over reacting, arguing, getting irritated, anxiety, deteriorating health, more of accidents, excessive smoking and drinking, sleeplessness etc.

Causes of occupational stress: Job stress results from various interactions of the worker and the environment of the work they perform their duties. Location, gender, environment and many other factors contribute to job stress. Causes of occupational stress are working conditions, long hours, workload and status. Economic factors are also result in stress. They are-pressure from investors, who can quickly withdraw their money from company stocks,

the lack of trade and professional unions in the workplace, the willingness of companies to swiftly lay off workers to cope with changing business environments.

Stress management: Stress management aimed at controlling a person's level of stress, especially chronic stress, usually for the purpose of and for the motive of improving everyday functioning.

Coping with stress: Stress is one of the most daunting obstacles to employee engagement in the modern workplace. In the work place, employee- environment fit should be the primary focus. If it's a good match, the employee is likely to be relaxed. A poor fit increases tension and stress. Some other measures which could prove beneficial in coping with stress are suggested below:

- Encourage workplace wellness.
- Allow for flexible hours and remote working.
- Encourage social activity.
- Create quiet time.
- Practice yoga and meditation
- Recognising the success of the employees.

About the Company

Toyota is the global market leader in sales of hybrid electric vehicles, and one of the largest companies to encourage the mass- market adoption of hybrid vehicles across the globe. Toyota is also a market leader in hydrogen fuel-cell vehicles. The Company was founded by Kiichiro Toyoda, 28th August 1937 eighty two years ago. Toyota's head quarter located in Toyota, Aichi, Japan. Toyota's corporate structure consisted of 370,870 employees worldwide and in December 2019, Toyota recognised as a tenth largest company in the world by its revenue 30,225,681 million.

Toyota Motor Corporation produces vehicles under five brands, including the Toyota brand, Hino, Lexus, Ranz and Daihatsu. It holds a 16.66% stake in Subaru Corporation, a 5.9% stake in Isuzu until 2018, a 5.5% stake in Mazda, as well as joint ventures with two in china (GAC Toyota and Sichuan FAW Toyota motor), one in India (Toyota Kirloskar), one in the Czech Republic (TPCA), along with several " non automotive" companies. TMC is part of the Toyota group, one of the largest conglomerates in Japan. Toyota's management philosophy

has evolved from the company's origins and has been reflected in the terms "Lean Manufacturing" and Just In Time Production, which it was instrumental in developing.

Literature review

R.G. Ratnawat and Dr. P.c. Jha, (2014), in their article, "Impact of job related stress on employee performance: A review and Research agenda" examined about the available literature to understand the phenomenon so as to develop appropriate stress management strategies to not only save the employees from variety of health problems but to improve their performance and the performance of the organization. The study identified 35 occupational stress inducers (OSI) were identified through a comprehensive review of articles and reports published in the literature of management and allied disciplines between 1990 and 2014. Study concluded with suggesting possible data analysis techniques for providing directions for future research.

Ms. P. Vinotha, Ms. R. Suriya and Ms. S. Valarmathi (2015), in their article, "A study on Industrial Health and Safety Measures in H& R Johnson India Pvt. Ltd. at Thennangudi" Examined about health and safety measures implemented by the company to improve the performance of the employees. The study concluded with focusing the safety equipment adopted by the company and how it protects the employees from the accident at the work spot.

K.D.V. Prasad, Dr. Rajesh Vaidya and V Anil Kumar,(2016), in their article , "Study on the causes of stress among the employees in IT sector and its effect on the employee performance at the workplace with special reference to International Agricultural Research Institute, Hyderabad: A Comparative Analysis" Examined about the comparative analysis of causes of stress among the employees and its effect on the employee performance at the workplace in International Agricultural Research Institute (IARI) and Information Technology Sector (ITS). The study also examined about level of difference if any, among the both the areas employees. The study concluded that impact of occupational stress on performance for the IARI employees is moderate and when compared with ITS. The results indicate that the job related stress in general and the stress factor job security in particular effects the employee performance in IT sector.

Ch Lakshmi Narahari, (2017), in her article, "A study on stress management among the empolees of ITES (BPO) – Companies" Identified about the reasons of stress among BPO employees and the ways used by employees to cope with the stress generated at work place.

The study also examined about the maximum number of employees in BPO remains stress. Majority of the employees try to find solution to relieve them from stress and study concludes with suggesting measures to over stress that affects their physical and mental health.

Dr. K. Premkumar, Dr.P.Ganapathi and Dr. Sumathipremkumar(2018), in their article, “ A study on Stress Management and Coping Strategies with reference to IT companies in Tamil Nadu” Examined about stress level among IT employees. The study concludes with stress coping strategies like stress management programmes, physical activities planned in job design, life style modification programmes, finding triggers and stressors, supportive organization culture, stress counselling programmes and spiritual programmes.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify Safety measures implemented by the company for the wellbeing of employees.
2. To study the stress management programmes implemented by the company.

Research Methodology

The validity of any research lies to a great extent in the methodology followed. The methodology can be defined as, “ A systematic and scientific description of how a particular study has been carried out”. This study is coordinated by using the secondary data. For this purpose company website, various books, magazines, journals are made in order to complete the study.

Limitations of the study

Every study has its limitations due to the unpredictable environment. This study has been conducted for a shorter duration of time due to constraints.

Discussions of the study

Safety measures implemented by Toyota Motor Corporation

As per the study it is found that the company experienced such unprecedented accidents as injuries caused by inappropriate handling of old equipment, to which company made alterations to improve its usability but company not notified sufficiently of such alterations, and other cases of injuries caused by a change in the placement of goods. As a result, the company recorded the frequency rate of lost work day injuries of 0.22. But company ultimate goal is to create safe and secure workplaces for everyone, where each and every associate can

exercise their diverse potentials and play active roles. So, the company implemented a several safety measures to enhance the productivity level of the employees.

- The study exhibits that company strives to prevent industrial accidents and occupational disorders as well as realize better work environments by making equipment more immune to accidents or disorders as early as in their design stage.
- The study reveals that company continued to promote primarily ‘’ activities aimed at establishing a safety – oriented culture and safety and health measures from human, object and administrative standpoints based on risk assessment’’.
- As per the study it is found that in establishing a safety culture, the company expanded the target group of rank- based safety workshops. The company also seek to nurture a mutual enlightenment- based safety culture, in which company encourage workers to exercise point- and- call practices and remind those persons showing unsafe behaviour to instill basic safety procedures.
- As per the study it is found that for risk assessment, the company aims to ensure the safety and security of the work place and reduce risks by investigating and visualizing latent hazard sources within the workplace. As the investigation of risks requires information on past accidents and potentially serious near- accidents, company break down and organize such information into smaller stages of accident occurrence and disseminate it to improve the quality of risk assessment in each work place.
- The study exhibits that company undertakes measures to prevent explosions caused by combustible gas and after repeated testing, company successfully come up with a gas concentration detection system with excellent maintainability.
- The study reveals that company also adopts several promoting activities to prevent slip and fall accident like installing antislip tapes and hazard markings on uneven floors and stairs as well as fixing shoe cleaning mats on to the floor.

Occupational Stress management measures of Toyota Motor Corporation

The Japanese government launched a new occupational health policy called stress check system. This system mandates that all workplaces with 50 or more employees conduct the stress check program for workers at least once in a year. This program began with amendment of the industrial Safety and Health law in 2014 which became effective on Dec 1, 2015. The uniqueness of stress check programme in Japan is that it focuses on psychosocial

stress of individual workers. The rationale for mandating the stress check program is threefold- (1) decreasing the risk of mental health problems in workers by increasing their awareness of their own stress through periodic surveys and feedback, (2) decreasing work related stressors by analyzing group stress survey results and improving the work environment, and (3) preventing mental health problems by screening for high-risk workers and providing them with opportunities to have physicians interviews.

As per the government order Toyota motor corporation introduced stress check system and feedback the check results to all participants and workplaces with suggestions for improvement. Company also makes arrangements for individual interview with a doctor for those wishing to do so. In order to work with less stress company focus on creating a better work environment for old age associates by adjusting the height of jigs in production lines and modifying processes to compensate for deterioration of vision. In addition company holds seminars for an active life for associates reaching the age of 50 and 55 to give them an opportunity to envision life and work for the next 10 years.

Conclusion

Toyota is one of the largest companies to encourage the mass- market adoption of hybrid vehicles across the globe. This study was carried out as per the schedule and it was found that the organization has provided several safety and stress management measures to enhance the productivity as well as mental health of the employees. The productivity of the workforce is the most decisive factor as far as the success of an organization is concerned. Productivity in turn is dependent on the psychosocial well being of the employees. Stress can affect one's health, work performance, social life and the relationship with family members. So, it is the duty lies with the organization to develop further more stress reduction techniques like yoga, meditation, encouraging social activity, recognizing success of the employees in order to overcome up with the occupational stress level of employees.

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